

Digital Transformation in Education: resilient to a new health crisis now?

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ABSTRACT

The Digital Transformation within the Dutch higher education has gone through a revolution on account of the COVID-19 pandemic. The entire higher education suddenly needed to be provided digitally. Since the higher education institutions were not digitally resilient before the crisis started, several digital products were rapidly introduced to be able to keep the education going. Online communication tools, virtual classrooms and online exam environments have been widely implemented. This digital transformation has, however, not passed by without any troubles; there was no experience among education institutions with this situation. Due to the high pressure, most institutes however still succeeded in providing education online successfully. In the end, it can be concluded that due to the accelerated digital transformation within the Dutch higher education, the digital resilience of this sector has considerably improved. This research looks deeper into the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic on the digital transformation of the Dutch higher education and therefore to what extent higher education is digitally resilient to new health crises now.

Keywords

Digital resilience, digital transformation, higher education, health crisis

INTRODUCTION

COVID-19; the virus that has changed the whole world. So is the Dutch higher education. The pandemic has created an extraordinary medical, economic and social emergency. To keep the spread of the virus under control, the Dutch government adopted a lockdown policy which led to closing high schools for several months. This resulted in a massive surge of online activity for education. Where for example, all the lessons were given physically before the pandemic started, suddenly the lessons were supposed to be given remotely. This occurrence predestined a massive disruption for the education sector. Resulting in a fast-moving process

of digital transformation of the education system to support the online learning opportunities, where the online education needed to be directly available for the students (Major, 2020).

To be able to provide all the lessons remotely, a new infrastructure was needed to be set up and prepared in a few days, which required big investments and creative efforts from the IT departments. This new way of conducting education that was forced by the pandemic, still has its impact on the 'post-pandemic' time. The digital transformation of education exposed the strengths and weaknesses of online learning, and created new opportunities for reshaping the manner in which education is given in the higher Dutch education system in 'post-pandemic' time. Hybrid classes and online learning modules are indispensable in higher education (Konkin, 2021). And so is meeting digitally with fellow students or teachers, which is also commonly-known and widely adopted within education nowadays.

This study will look into the digital transformation during the COVID-19 pandemic and how this digital transformation impacted the digital resilience of the Dutch higher education towards a new health crisis. This will be done by stating the digital transformation of higher education, the characteristics of a health crisis, the problems during the digital transformation, and information about when higher education is resilient to a new health crisis.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

Currently, there is little knowledge amongst the Dutch educational institutes about what the effects will be on the operational processes when a similar situation to COVID-19 occurs. Did the schools learn from the COVID-19 pandemic when it comes to being digital resilient or will they struggle when a new health crisis occurs?

Existing literature describes that during the COVID-19 pandemic, Dutch educational institutes were not resilient to the COVID-19 pandemic. Many

schools had to implement a lot of changes in their operational processes to cope with the effects of the pandemic. According to Major (2020), the digital transformation by the adoption of technology for teaching and learning was a key factor for the Dutch educational institutes to continue their processes and provide their services to the students.

Evidence of the conjectures stated above that digital transformation had a big impact on Dutch educational institutes when coping with the COVID-19 pandemic. Looking back at the pandemic, in general the digital resilience of the schools was not sufficient. After the pandemic, there is a knowledge gap about the level of digital resilience after the digital transformation the educational institutions went through during the COVID-19 pandemic. This is also mentioned by Toquero (2020) by an implication for further study about the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic to the educational system and gathering scientific evidence on how educational institutions can effectively respond to another future virus outbreak. This research will contribute to this by creating an overview of the digital transformation during the pandemic and how this transformation affected the digital resilience of higher education towards a new health crisis. This level of digital resilience will give information about how effective the Dutch higher education institutions can respond to another health crisis.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

To examine the effects of digital transformation on the digital resilience of higher Dutch educational institutions, the following research question was developed: "To what extent is higher Dutch education resilient to a new health crisis, as a result of the digital transformation caused by the COVID-19 pandemic?"

The following sub-questions were developed in order to provide an answer to the main question of this research:

- What are the characteristics of a health crisis?
- What digital transformation did the Dutch higher education go through as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic?
- What problems did higher education face when they made a digital transformation during COVID?
- When is higher education resilient to a new health crisis?

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Conceptual model

In this research, the digital transformation of education is defined as the integration of digital technology into all areas of education, delivering value to learners and fundamentally changing the way they operate. In our research, this variable will act as an independent variable (Kim, H, 2021).

Digital resilience for a new health crisis is defined as an organization's ability to continue to operate through an impairment, and to stay in business while minimizing customer harm, reputational damage, and financial loss. In our research, the impairment will be a new potential health crisis (Mehedintu, 2022).

COVID-19 is defined as an infectious disease caused by the SARS-CoV-2 virus which caused a global pandemic. This pandemic resulted in different types of measurements that were taken by the Dutch government which Dutch educational institutions had to cope with.

As mentioned before, COVID-19 had an effect on the digital transformation within Dutch educational institutions caused by the measurements that were taken by the Dutch government. This research investigates how COVID-19 impacted the digital transformation within the Dutch educational institutions and what the effect of digital transformation is on these institutions looking at the resilience for a potential upcoming health crisis.

Therefore, digital transformation is an independent variable in this research, while digital resilience for a new health crisis is the dependent variable for our research. COVID-19 impacts the independent variable causing an effect on the digital transformation within Dutch educational institutions which enhances the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable.

Hypotheses

Based on the conceptual model, the following hypothesis were formulated:

H1: The digital transformation within Dutch educational institutes has a positive effect on the digital resilience of Dutch educational institutions for a new health crisis.

H2: COVID-19 has a positive effect on the digital transformation within Dutch education institutions.

METHODOLOGY

For the theoretical research questions, existing literature has been reviewed to form a conclusive answer. The literature which is used for the results section is purely academic literature which is peer-reviewed and relevant for this research. The results of the literature research can be found in the results chapter.

To be able to form a comprehensive, well-substantiated answer on the research question, archival research is conducted in this research. The research has a deductive approach whereby hypotheses based on existing theory become developed, and then designing a research strategy to test the hypotheses. The results from archival research give insights into external data, which is peer-reviewed. Due to the recent COVID-19 health crisis which disrupted society and education, there has been conducted a lot of research on this topic, so there is already existing knowledge for it. For this reason, archival research is used to answer the research questions. To ensure the archival research is valid, search engines such as Google Scholar and Worldcat were consulted. These different search engines were used to obtain information from different academic sources, in order to ensure the validity of the literature. Furthermore, there have been set up several criteria for choosing the articles, which are provided in Table 1:

Table 1 – selection criteria articles

Criteria	
Date published	> 2008
Cited by	> 15
Author Citations	> 15
References	> 20

RESULTS

Characteristics health crisis

A health crisis is a difficult situation that affects humans in one or more geographic areas, varying from local outbreaks to the entire planet. In general, health crises have significant impacts on society, including community health, the public health system, and the economy. Health crises could be a result of disease, industrial processes or poor policy (Gérvás & Meneu, 2010). Its impact on society depends on the severity of the crisis, which is often measured by the number of people that are affected by its geographical extent, or the disease or death of the pathogenic process from which it originates (Gravitz, 2011).

Generally, there are three different types of health crises:

- Ecological
- Food
- Toxic (epidemic/pandemic)

In the first place, there are the ecological crises. These crises occur when changes to the environment of a population endangers its continued survival. Examples of ecological crises could be natural disasters like earthquakes and floods, but also the increase in temperature or the decrease of significant rainfalls as a result of climate change (Galaz et al., 2010). These occurrences could lead to a health crisis, paired with a shortage of food and clean drinking water.

In the second place, there are the food crises. These kinds of crises occur especially often in third world countries, mainly because of shortage of food. This is often partly due to poor soil fertility, failing government policies and climate change. Eventually, a food crisis is often paired with femininity, which could endanger the global health of a population and lead to a health crisis (Chand, 2009). However, also developed countries are facing health problems related to food: obesity. People who eat too much unhealthy food, have a great chance to deal with obesity. In Western countries, the amount of people who have obesity is rising, which could potentially lead to a health crisis (Brown et al., 2009).

These two kinds of health crises are not very common in the recent history of The Netherlands, and do not contribute to a disruption of the Dutch higher education. A toxic health crisis, however, has had the Dutch higher education in its grip for the last 2,5 years, due to the COVID-19 pandemic. For this paper, the focus lies on a toxic health crisis, which (temporarily) leads to another form of providing education.

Within the toxic part of health crises, there are two types of it: epidemic and pandemic. An epidemic is a (virus) outbreak that spreads over a larger geographical area, with a sudden increase in the number of people with a condition greater than was expected. A pandemic is an epidemic that spreads globally. Viruses that can cause pandemics often get transmitted very quickly from one person to the next, and because of movements of people over the entire planet, the infections can be brought to new parts of the world within hours (Grennan, 2019).

A disease is considered a pandemic when it consists of the following characteristics: wide geographic extension, disease movement, high attack rates and explosiveness, minimal population immunity, novelty, infectiousness, contagiousness, and severity (Morens et al., 2009). A disease with such characteristics, thus a pandemic, could lead to a substantial disruption of the society and can provoke a public health crisis (Casey et al., 2020).

In the COVID-19 example, the virus was considered as very infectious and contagious, so the government introduced several restrictions with the hope to decrease the spread of the virus. The core message was to avoid gatherings with other people as much as possible. Everyone was thus forced to stay at home as much as possible. This meant to be a major shift in people's behaviour, which means everybody felt the effects of the public health crisis.

Digital transformation higher education during COVID-19 pandemic

Numerous social and economic facets of human life, especially the educational system, were impacted by the COVID-19 epidemic. Although there were many obstacles, such as inadequate connectivity and a lack of technological know-how in using online tools, the educational institution nevertheless provided high-quality education remotely by using a variety of learning options. According to Kim, H, (2021), the COVID-19 pandemic had a detrimental effect on the sector of education, providing new opportunities for students. However, despite the fact that schools were closed and there was little direct interaction among students, it had forced them to use technological means to further their education.

Digital transformation was the key for the educational institutions to keep their teaching going. The main digital transformation that these institutions went through was a virtual classroom.

Virtual Classrooms

Virtual classrooms were introduced in most educational institutions. Using conference tools,

such as Microsoft Teams, Zoom or Google Meet, classes and exams were given online to the students. The human connection that a physical classroom environment offers is a crucial component of education. In a virtual classroom, teachers and students can also interact in real time. Students can ask questions and engage in peer interaction just as they would in a traditional classroom, but now online (Kim, H, 2021).

According to Mukhtar, K. Javed, K., Arooj, M., & Sethi, A. (2020), online learning helped to assure distant learning, was manageable, and provided students with easy access to instructors and learning resources. Additionally, it cut down on additional costs and the usage of resources for travel. Administrative responsibilities like recording lectures and recording attendance were made easier. Online learning strategies, in the opinion of both the students and the professors, promoted student-centeredness during the lockdown. The student was now a self-directed learner who could learn at any moment throughout the day asynchronously.

Unfortunately, the transformation to virtual classrooms did not only have advantages. According to Mukhtar, K., Javed, K., Arooj, M., & Sethi, A. (2020), practical and clinical work cannot be taught or learned via online learning modalities. They could only impart knowledge and evaluate it. During online lectures, teachers were unable to evaluate students' understanding because there was no quick feedback. The students also mentioned the difficulty of online learning and their short attention spans as drawbacks. Teachers have also reported that students sometimes misbehaved and attempted to use online resources during exams. Some students who were accustomed to traditional educational methods, are suddenly required to exercise self-discipline and time management, which was a difficult transition.

Communication Technologies and other technologies

Besides using conference tools for the virtual classroom, other communication tools were used more and more during the COVID-19 pandemic. These communication tools can be divided into the following categories: conference tools, publishing and sharing technologies, social networks and electronic mail (Santos, Helena & Batista, João & Marques, Rui Pedro, 2019).

Another type of technology that surfaced during the COVID-19 pandemic, was a technology for online exams. This technology enabled students to make exams at home.

Major problems coming with the digital transformation

To get a clear image of how resilient the Dutch high education is, when there was another health crisis, it is important to know what problems they faced during the digital transformation in the COVID-19 crisis. The intention from the beginning of the lockdown has been to allow educational activities and exams to continue as much as possible to keep study delays to a minimum, however the Dutch government announced a national lockdown, thus the high education needed to change the way of lectures, exams and programs (De Boer, 2020). This was the biggest challenge that national education systems ever faced (Daniel, 2020).

In response to this lockdown, education institutions have started offering an online program, as stated in sub-question one. Most universities did not have experience in dealing with a pandemic such as COVID-19 and other natural disasters. Thus, this was their first significant experience with changing the system, methodologies and society of education, which led to many different challenges for students, teachers and institutes (Izumi, 2020). The institutes had to handle very quickly, because there was limited time and education had to keep going, short term decisions were made, without thinking of long-term effects.

With the change from traditional teaching to online teaching in classrooms, more challenges became clear. There were two major problems which the education system faced (Kim, 2021). The first major challenge was the effectiveness of these online classes, which is necessary to keep study delay to a minimum. Every institute had to adapt their way of teaching and examination regulations in a very short time and under great pressure. In addition to that, the Minister of Education allowed the institutes to decide how they would test for themselves (VSNU 2020). This led to very different methods by the different institutes. For example, some institutes, like the UvA, installed surveillance software so they could check if a student did not cheat during an exam, but the other would not use such a system because it would violate students' privacy (De Boer, 2020).

This led to concerns about the quality of education from politicians and from students. Students did not want to pay the tuition fee because the quality was not good enough. And some politicians wanted to use 'mystery guests' to control the quality of the education (Belleman, 2020). So, there was a lack of general national policy, on which the Dutch higher education could rely on.

The second challenge for the high education institutes were financial problems. The financial instability, in the form of unexpected cost and

potential reductions in revenue, due to the cancellation of enrollment by domestic or international students (Izumi, 2020). The delay of research is another big financial issue, due to the delay of research funded by third parties (De Boer, 2020). The high education institutes needed to find a way to still make an income for all their different costs. Besides covering the standard cost, the cost of E-learning are also high. The institutes need to get licenses, teachers training and operating cost (Maatuk, 2022).

Factors to determine digital resilience against health crisis

For a company to survive and thrive during a health crisis digital resilience is essential. This is because resilience of a platform ecosystem is available to cope with shocks and for a company to be resistant to future disruptions (Mehedintu, 2022). For this reason, it is important to define when higher education is resilient to a new health crisis, this so the characteristics of a resilient higher education can be used to determine to what extent higher Dutch education is resilient to a new health crisis, as a result of the digital transformation caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. In general, a company must develop a business model based on organizational culture to build the digital resilience of that company (Senqupta et al., 2021). This is to direct the allocation of investment towards digital innovation, which can be supported by employees.

To determine the digital resilience of a company, eight predictors can be used that have an influence on the digital resilience of a company. Each predictor has a positive influence on the digital resilience of that company, so if a higher education can make sure they have a high score on the different predictors they will be resilient to a new health crisis. The eight variables that influence the digital resilience are: 1) security investments (SI); (2) remote working (RW); (3) cloud migration (CM); (4) digital transformation investments (DX); (5) digital adaptation (DA); (6) digital acceleration (DC); (7) digital core (DO); (8) digital innovation investments (DI); (Mehedintu, 2022) In figure one the SEM measurement model shows the influence of each predictor on the dependent variable Digital resilience, based on this figure you can see that the variables with a direct influence are the Digital core (DO) and the Digital innovation (DI) of a company.

Figure 1. SEM measurement model. (Mehedintu, 2022)

Based on this research, a conclusion can be made that the digital core and the digital innovation of a company directly determine the digital resilience of a company. These direct predictors are influenced by six other aspects of higher education that are mentioned at a later point in the research. This means that Dutch higher education needs to have a high digital core and innovation to be resilient to a new health crisis. For higher education to have a digital core they can use virtual individual work, adopt industry 4.0 technologies in the automation process, and to what extent the education achieved digitizing the business. The best way for higher education to be digital innovative is to introduce and use digital products in the way they educate students. Other ways to have a good digital core and digital innovation, is to improve the other predictors that have an influence on the level of digital core and innovation. Table 2 shows how higher education can improve the six other predictors mentioned in the measurement model.

Table 2, Predictors, Improvement possibilities, coding for measurement model (Mehedintu, 2022)

Predictor	Improvement possibility	Coding
Security investments	Internet of Things security	SI1

	Solutions application security	SI2
	Network security	SI3
	Cloud security	SI4
Remote Working	Different possibilities to work remote	RW1/RW2/RW3
Cloud migration	SaaS/PaaS/IaaS in the company	CM1/CM2/CM3
	Hybrid model	CM4
Digital transformation investments	Interaction through the website	DX1
	Mobile applications in processes	DX2
	Social networks in the digital transformation	DX3
	Conversational interfaces	DX4
Digital adaptation	IT projects to support vulnerable processes discovered in times of crisis	DA1
	IT projects in support of the new operational requirements generated by the implementation of technology 4.0/pandemic crisis	DA2
Digital acceleration	IT projects that model business innovation	DC1

Concluding all the information, Dutch higher education should have a high level of digital security, remote working, cloud migration, digital transformation, digital adaptation, digital acceleration, digital core, and digital innovation. This is because these aspects of the company have an influence on the digital resilience of the company. So if the different aspects of the company have a high level they will have a positive impact on the digital resilience resulting in a higher education that is resilient to a new health crisis.

DISCUSSION

According to the results, the Dutch higher education has gone through a considerable digital transformation due to the COVID-19 pandemic. The public health crisis, which had the characteristic to have a remarkable impact on everyone's life, has led to significant changes in the manner how education was provided. The results of the archival research show that the digital transformation has mainly resulted in digitizing business processes, introducing digital products, like online classrooms, the use of digital communication methods and an increased application of IT for innovation. Education was mainly provided through virtual classrooms, supported by online meeting tools like Microsoft Teams and Zoom. Also, the taking of exams were often executed online too. This accelerated digital transformation offered opportunities to the higher education to become more digitally resilient. However, this sudden digital transformation did not go without any problems; education institutes needed to deal with several challenges. Difference in teaching and testing education, but also financial problems were an issue. Aside from that, there were concerns about the quality of education and teachers and students found it hard to run practical classes online.

As is stated, institutes have accelerated the digitization of their education, and discovered a new way of providing education. Consequently, the results show that higher education now has better instruments to provide education in different ways, thus also virtually, which significantly contributed to the resilience for eventual new health crises.

CONCLUSION

Looking at the archival research and the discussion the research question can be answered:

“To what extent is higher Dutch education resilient to a new health crisis, as a result of the digital transformation caused by the COVID-19 pandemic?”

The Dutch higher education has undergone an

enormous digital transformation, forced by the measures taken against the spread of COVID-19. There was little resilience before the crisis started, however the crisis has changed this in a short time. There are digital products introduced, to continue the education going, without meeting in real life. All these new technologies and types of education have improved the institutes' level of digital security, remote working, cloud migration, digital transformation, digital adaptation, digital acceleration, digital core, and digital innovation.

This fast transformation also introduced some serious troubles. There was no experience in how to deal with a health crisis, so there was no standard procedure, which every institute should follow. This led to the decrease of the education quality, which is the most important for Dutch higher education.

When there will be another toxic health crisis, which could affect education, the institutes will be better prepared due to the experience and the digitalisation. The Dutch government needs to give a strict guideline to follow by the institutes, otherwise the quality of education will decrease. It can be concluded that the Dutch higher education system is digital resilient for the time being if there is a general policy. Still, they need to be very alert for new technologies to help them keep the predictors at a high level.

The insights gained by this research will be useful for Dutch high education to help them prepare for a possible next health crisis.

Limitations & Further research

In this study, there are several (potential) limitations. These limitations are mainly a result of the short time period in which the research is conducted and the limited availability of resources. The study is fully based on archival research, which originates from reliable sources according to the requirements stated in the Methodology. These sources are sufficient to subtract information to answer the research question. However, in order to validate the research with practical findings, and increase its integrality, further research could conduct a survey among teachers and students to examine their view on the digital transformation of higher education.

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